

101132933 – AD-RIDDLE

Real-World Implementation, Deployment and Validation of Early Detection Tools and Lifestyle Enhancement

WP8 – Communications, Public Involvement, and Outreach

D8.1 AD-RIDDLE Communications Pack

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Due date	31/12/2024
Delivery date	17/12/2024
Deliverable type	R
Dissemination level	PU

This project is supported by the Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking (IHI JU) under grant agreement No. 101132933. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and COCIR, EFPIA, EuropaBio,

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	WP8 – Communications, Public Involvement, and Outreach	Version: v1.0 – Draft	
	Author(s): Angela Bradshaw and Cindy Birck (11-Alzheimer Europe)	Security: PU	2/34

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	Author(s): Angela Bradshaw and Cindy Birck (11-Alzheimer Europe)	Security: PU	3/34

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Description
V1.0	17 December	First Draft
VX.X	dd Mmm 2024	Comments
VX.X	dd Mmm 2024	Draft
VX.X	dd Mmm 2024	Final Version

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the AD-RIDDLE Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

RS: Region Stockholm, Karolinska Universitetssjukhuset - Sweden (**The Coordinator**)

KI: Karolinska Institutet, Department of Neurobiology, Care Sciences and Society - Sweden

FBHI: Stiftelsen Fingers Brain Health Institute - Sweden

UGOT: Goeteborgs Universitet - Sweden

ULUND: Lunds Universitet - Sweden

UEF: Itäلتältä-suomen Yliopisto, University of Eastern Finland - Finland

VUMC: Stichting VUmc - The Netherlands

UM: Universiteit Maastricht - The Netherlands

BBRC: Fundació Barcelonabeta Brain Research Center - Spain

SYNAPSE: Synapse Research Management Partners S.L - Spain

AE: Alzheimer Europe - Luxembourg

ADI: Alzheimer’s Disease International – United States

UNIPG: Universita Degli Studi di Perugia - Italy

GV: Gates Ventures LLC – United States (**The Co-Coordinator**)

DAC: Davos Alzheimer’s Collaborative - Switzerland

COMBINOSTICS: Combinostics Oy - Finland

Fujirebio: Fujirebio Europe NV - Belgium

SARD: Sanofi-Aventis Recherche & Development - France

C2N: C2N Diagnostics LLC – United States

neotiv GmbH: Neotiv GmbH - Germany

CCL: Cambridge Cognition Limited – United Kingdom

ULEIC: University of Leicester – United Kingdom

ICL: Imperial College of Science, Technology and medicine - United Kingdom

NICE: National Institute for Health and Care Excellence- United Kingdom

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IHI for the undertaking of the AD-RIDDLE project (101132933).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The AD-RIDDLE Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst AD-RIDDLE participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties’ obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The AD-RIDDLE Communications Pack (D8.1) is a technical report which describes the AD-RIDDLE communication channels, visual identity and communications guidelines. D8.1 complements the Communication and Dissemination Strategy (D8.2) which identifies how these communications elements will be used to achieve wide outreach and raise awareness of AD-RIDDLE in key audiences, thereby maximising the impact of AD-RIDDLE.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Work package 8 (WP8) is designed to support the communication activities of project partners, and to coordinate communication and dissemination through project-specific channels. The specific communications goals of WP8 aim to achieve wide outreach and raise awareness of AD-RIDDLE in key audiences, using carefully designed and selected tools, channels and materials.

D8.2 (Communication and Dissemination Strategy) was the first deliverable report for WP8, submitted in August 2024. The Communication and Dissemination Strategy is a living document that outlines the strategies, methods, channels, tools and activities that will be used to meet the IHI requirements for effective communication and dissemination, thereby maximising the impact of AD-RIDDLE.

D8.1 (AD-RIDDLE Communications Pack) is a technical report that complements the Communication and Dissemination Strategy, and describes the AD-RIDDLE communication channels (website, social media channels); visual identity (logo, branding, colour palette); and communications guidelines. These communications elements will apply and be used throughout the IHI funding period. Any refinements or updates in the coming years will be provided as annexes that can be appended to D8.1.

2. Communication channels and tools

Effective communication and dissemination of AD-RIDDLE’s achievements require the use of various tools, channels and materials to reach the identified audiences. The AD-RIDDLE consortium has started to design and produce several tools and channels needed to implement the communication plan. These include the AD-RIDDLE website (www.ad-riddle.org) and the AD-RIDDLE social media channels ([@AD_RIDDLE](#) on X/Twitter and [AD-RIDDLE](#) on LinkedIn); as well as tools such as the AD-RIDDLE logo & visual identity.

The table below briefly describes these channels and tools, explaining how and when they will be utilised throughout the project.

Tool & Channel	Focus	Target stakeholder	Frequency
Logo & visual identity	Branding to ensure consistent visual representation	All	Continuous
Website	Central hub for information, news and resources	All	Continuous
Social media channels	Increasing visibility of the project, engaging with the community, driving traffic to the project website	All	Weekly

2.1 AD-RIDDLE logo & visual identity

An **AD-RIDDLE Style Guide** was established at the start of the project, describing the logo, AD-RIDDLE colours, typography/photography, and other branding elements that will be used

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consistently throughout the project. The Style Guide is attached to this deliverable as **Annex 1**. Below, we summarise some of the key contents of the Style Guide.

The AD-RIDDLE logo serves as a visual identity for the project and is prominently displayed on all communication materials. Where relevant, the AD-RIDDLE logo will be used in conjunction with the IHI JU logo, the EU emblem and the logos of COCIR, EFPIA, EuropaBio, MedTech Europe and Vaccines Europe to acknowledge funding and support from these entities.

The AD-RIDDLE logo was developed at the very beginning of the project to ensure a unified image from the outset. The logotype consists of a modern wordmark interwoven with a Light Red line that represents the journey towards better detection, diagnosis and treatment of Alzheimer’s disease. It comes in several versions and colours (Fig.1), including with and without a descriptor, to ensure appropriate use in diverse communication scenarios.

The primary colours used in the logo are Dark Blue (HEX 212442), Light Red (HEX FF8080), Light Blue (HEX EBF2F5) and White (HEX FFFFFFFF). The secondary colours consist of Yellow (HEX F7DD5D), Green (, Teal, Blue and Purple, for use in charts, graphs and informational graphics. The logotype and colours are approved for use across all communications online and in print.

Fig.1. AD-RIDDLE logos in different colourways and formats. Top to bottom: for white backgrounds; for light blue backgrounds; for dark backgrounds; for horizontal & short formats; for square and tall formats.

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The **AD-RIDDLE typography** consists of a modern geometric sans font called URW DIN that is easy to read at all sizes. The primary recommended font weights are URW DIN Demi for headlines and subheads, and URW DIN Regular for supporting text. These are approved for use across all communications online and in print. Additional font weights from the same font family can be used to create more complex hierarchies when needed. Do not use too many font weights or font sizes in a communication. Where URW DIN is not available, Arial is used as a secondary font.

The **AD-RIDDLE Pathway Graphic** is a modular Light Red line derived from the AD-RIDDLE logotype. It is approved for use across all communications online and in print. As indicated above, the Pathway Graphic represents the journey towards better detection, diagnosis, and treatment of Alzheimer’s disease.

2.2 AD-RIDDLE Website

The AD-RIDDLE website is a **key channel** for external outreach, communication and dissemination, serving as a central hub for all project-related information and activities. The website can be accessed at <https://ad-riddle.org/>.

The website content is managed using the Contentful Content Management System (CMS), which is a headless CMS. This means that the front end (website/user interface) is separated from the back end (data storage) with content accessed through API calls. AD-RIDDLE data is stored in a dedicated Azure environment with staging and production platforms. Unpublished updates are displayed in the staging environment and versioning is controlled via the CMS, which has MFA.

The first version of the AD-RIDDLE website is structured around three pages:

- **Homepage:** this scrollable page presents the high-level mission of AD-RIDDLE; outlines the challenges being addressed in the project; details the contents of the AD-RIDDLE toolbox platform; and highlights the fact that AD-RIDDLE is a public-private partnership. Finally, it provides a signup form for the AD-RIDDLE newsletter, and a footer with contact details and the funding acknowledgement (Fig.2)
- **About:** this scrollable page lists the different partners in the AD-RIDDLE consortium, with a mid-section that includes quotes from the project leads, and a lower section that re-iterates the call to action to subscribe to the AD-RIDDLE newsletter, and the same footer as described for the homepage.
- **News and Resources:** This page includes articles providing updates on the project, also serving as a repository for resources.

The website will be progressively updated throughout the project to reflect new content and respond to the changing needs of the project and its stakeholders. Planned updates include:

- **Content enrichment:** Adding detailed information on the project's progress and achievements
- **Expanded News and Resources section:** Including interviews with project members, publications and public deliverables

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- **Structural enhancements:** Adjusting the website structure to better serve stakeholder needs as the project evolves.

Collaborating to solve a major public health challenge

Today, almost **9 million people** are living with Alzheimer's disease or dementia in Europe, a figure that is expected to double by 2050.

There is a pressing need for effective preventive, diagnostic and therapeutic solutions, implemented at scale, and for patients and their families to have the ability to understand and manage their care.

AD-RIDDLE will offer healthcare providers a suite of validated solutions to match patients with the right interventions at the right time.

[LEARN MORE](#)

Estimated number of people living with Alzheimer's disease or dementia in Europe

The AD-RIDDLE toolbox platform

Every healthcare system and practitioner should have the ability to make the best choice for their patients. AD-RIDDLE's modular toolbox platform will provide support at all stages of the clinical pathway to speed up patient access to healthcare providers and precision medicine.

Digital community engagement portal

AD-RIDDLE's digital portal will include self-guided assessment tools for EU citizens, pathways for timely referral to healthcare providers, and tailored resources that connect to the next best step.

Screening tools

Providers will have access to a suite of validated digital cognitive assessments and blood-based biomarkers, intended to increase accuracy in risk detection and early diagnosis.

Decision support toolkit

The toolkit for healthcare providers will unite best-in-class research, science, and outcomes data to enable differential diagnosis and inform personalized plans for prevention and care.

Personalized patient therapies

Patients will be matched with the right interventions at the right time, including lifestyle interventions and pharmacological treatments.

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A flexible, scalable platform

The AD-RIDDLE platform will allow for flexible adaptation and application in diverse settings, from memory clinics, to primary care, to the broader population outside of healthcare systems.

A real-world testing study will be conducted in these settings across 6 European countries, and will provide extensive evidence to support implementation of diagnostic tools, treatments and lifestyle interventions. To facilitate new findings on Alzheimer's disease research, data from the AD-RIDDLE study will be hosted in a GDPR-compliant manner on the [European Platform for Neurodegenerative Diseases](#).

[SIGN UP FOR OUR NEWSLETTER](#)

The people behind AD-RIDDLE

The AD-RIDDLE consortium unites 24 public and private leaders from across Europe.

[LEARN MORE ABOUT OUR PARTNERS](#)

Stay up to date on AD-RIDDLE news

Sign up for our newsletter for updates on the development of the AD-RIDDLE toolbox platform.

Business email address *

First Name *

Last Name *

Country

Organisation

I am a...

SUBSCRIBE

Fig. 2: Homepage of the AD-RIDDLE website

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2.3 AD-RIDDLE social media channels

Social media platforms enable connections between millions of users worldwide. The presence of AD-RIDDLE on social media is essential for increasing project visibility and for reaching a broad and diverse audience, including researchers, clinicians, policymakers and the general public.

Currently, AD-RIDDLE uses the most popular social networks with a presence on **X** (formerly Twitter) ([@AD_RIDDLE](#)) (Fig.3) and [LinkedIn](#), (Fig.4).

Fig. 3: AD-RIDDLE X handle

Fig. 4: AD-RIDDLE LinkedIn profile

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The X and LinkedIn profiles for AD-RIDDLE have been designed in accordance with the AD-RIDDLE Style Guide (Annex 1), including a pathway graphic, the AD-RIDDLE logo, and a funding acknowledgement.

In addition to X/Twitter and LinkedIn, we are also investigating the use of other social media channels such as **Facebook** to foster community engagement and **YouTube** to share interviews with key stakeholders and provide a repository of recorded events.

2.4 IHI Communication guidelines

AD-RIDDLE is an IHI-funded project and must adhere to the **IHI communication guidelines**. The project grant agreement details the rules for communication activities. All project partners are expected to familiarise themselves with these rules and ensure compliance in their communication efforts. For more detailed information, please refer to article 17 (Communication, Dissemination and Visibility) in Annex 3.

All project communication activities, including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material (brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc.), and dissemination activities in electronic form, via traditional or social media, must acknowledge IHI support. This also applies to any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies, or major results funded by the grant. The requirements include:

- **Funding Acknowledgement:** All communications must include a statement acknowledging IHI funding.

“This project is supported by the Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking (IHI JU) under grant agreement No. 101132933. The JU receives support from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and COCIR, EFPIA, EuropaBio, MedTech Europe and Vaccines Europe, with Davos Alzheimer’s Collaborative, Combinostics OY., Cambridge Cognition Ltd., C2N Diagnostics LLC, and neotiv GmbH.”

- **Disclaimer:** Communications must include a disclaimer.

“Funded by the European Union, the private members, UKRI, and the contributing partners of the IHI JU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the aforementioned parties. None of the aforementioned parties can be held responsible for them.”

- **Logos:** the IHI JU logo, the EU emblem accompanied by the words Co-funded by the European Union, the logos of COCIR, EFPIA, EuropaBio, MedTech Europe, and Vaccines Europe.

In the case of dissemination of results, the IHI guidelines state that the results of the project must be disseminated promptly and in a publicly accessible format, subject to restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules, or legitimate interests. Beneficiaries intending to disseminate their results must provide at least 15 days' advance notice to other beneficiaries, unless

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agreed otherwise. This notice should include sufficient information about the results to be disseminated. Additionally, open-access must be provided for peer-reviewed scientific publications.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1 – AD-RIDDLE Style Guide

IDENTITY STYLE GUIDE

Version 1
December 2023

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LOGOTYPE

The AD-RIDDLE logotype consists of a modern wordmark interwoven with a Light Red line that represents the journey towards better detection, diagnosis, and treatment of Alzheimer's disease. It should be used across all communications online and in print.

The AD-RIDDLE logotype comes in several versions and colors, including with and without a descriptor. The preferred version is the full-color logotype with descriptor. Shown here are the approved background colors. Always choose the correct logotype based on these approved background colors.

The AD-RIDDLE logotype clear space is defined by the width of the letter 'A' around all four sides as shown here. The minimum size is defined by the height of the full logotype, including the Light Red line, and is 70 px tall online and 0.5" or 13 mm in print as shown here.

Full-color logotypes with descriptor
Approved for use on light backgrounds

Ideal for horizontal and short formats

Ideal for square and tall formats

Full-color logotype
Approved for use on White or Light Blue backgrounds

Logotype clear space
Defined by the width of letter 'A' around all four sides

Logotype minimum size
Defined by the height of the full logotype

Full-color logotype reversed
Approved for use on Dark Blue backgrounds

LOGOTYPE DO NOT'S

Avoid the following when creating AD-RIDDLE communications online and in print.

Do not modify or distort logotype

Do not alter logotype color

Do not add drop shadow or reflections

Do not use logotype on background colors that lack sufficient contrast

Do not combine with graphic elements

Do not place over complex photography

COLOR

The AD-RIDDLE primary colors consist of Dark Blue, Light Red, Light Blue, and White. These are approved for use across all communications online and in print.

Dark Blue should always be used in place of black when typesetting text. On account of its vibrant tone, Light Red should not be used when typesetting text. See page 7 for additional guidance on approved color combinations when typesetting text.

The AD-RIDDLE secondary colors consist of Yellow, Green, Teal, Blue, and Purple. These should only be used in charts, graphs, and information graphics to highlight important data. Do not use the Secondary Palette outside of charts, graphs, and information graphics.

Primary Colors

Dark Blue

Approved for use in logotype, text, backgrounds, graphics

HEX 212442
CMYK C=91 M=86 Y=44 K=44

White

Approved for use in logotype, text, backgrounds, graphics

HEX FFFFFFFF
CMYK C=0 M=0 Y=0 K=0

Light red

Approved for use in logotype and Pathway Graphic

HEX FF8080
CMYK C=0 M=60 Y=38 K=0

Light Blue

Approved for use in backgrounds

HEX EBF2F5
CMYK C=8 M=2 Y=2 K=0

Secondary Colors

Yellow

Approved for use in charts and graphs

HEX F7DD5D
CMYK C=4 M=8 Y=76 K=0

Green

Approved for use in charts and graphs

HEX 86D168
CMYK C=50 M=0 Y=78 K=0

Teal

Approved for use in charts and graphs

HEX 6FD8C7
CMYK C=51 M=0 Y=30 K=0

Blue

Approved for use in charts and graphs

HEX 3EB2F9
CMYK C=61 M=16 Y=0 K=0

Purple

Approved for use in charts and graphs

HEX C467E5
CMYK C=28 M=62 Y=0 K=0

COLOR DO NOT'S

Avoid the following when creating AD-RIDDLE communications online and in print.

Do not modify approved brand colors

Do not introduce new colors

Do not create gradients

Do not use Light Red or black for text

Do not use secondary colors for text

Do not use color combinations without sufficient background contrast

TYPOGRAPHY

The AD-RIDDLE typography consists of a modern geometric sans font called URW DIN that is easy to read at all sizes.

The primary recommended font weights are URW DIN Demi for headlines and subheads, and URW DIN Regular for supporting text. These are approved for use across all communications online and in print. Additional font weights from the same font family can be used to create more complex hierarchies when needed. Do not use too many font weights or font sizes in a communication.

When typesetting text, always use the approved typography color combinations shown here that all meet a minimum 4.5:1 color contrast ratio. This ensures all communications are compliant and meet WCAG 2.2 accessibility requirements.

Dark Blue should always be used in place of black when typesetting text. On account of its vibrant tone, Light Red should not be used when typesetting text.

If you need to purchase a license for the font, please click the following [link](#).

In instances where the URW DIN font may not be available, such as PowerPoint, the designated backup font is Arial.

URW DIN Demi

Approved for use across all communications

Aa

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuüvwxyzåö
ABCDEFGHIJKLMONPQRSTUVWXYZÅÖ
0123456789.,;:!?

Advancing Solutions for Alzheimer's Disease

We revolutionize how Alzheimer's Disease is detected, diagnosed, prevented, and treated, enabling better disease intervention and prevention.

Typography Color Combinations

Which meet WCAG 2.2 accessibility requirements

URW DIN Regular

Approved for use across all communications

Aa

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuüvwxyzåö
ABCDEFGHIJKLMONPQRSTUVWXYZÅÖ
0123456789.,;:!?

Advancing Solutions for Alzheimer's Disease

We revolutionize how Alzheimer's Disease is detected, diagnosed, prevented, and treated, enabling better disease intervention and prevention.

TYPOGRAPHY DO NOT'S

Avoid the following when creating AD-RIDDLE communications online and in print.

Do not introduce new fonts

**Advancing Solutions for
Alzheimer's Disease**

Do not mix font weights in headlines

Advancing Solutions for
Alzheimer's Disease

Do not distort typography

**Advancing Solutions for
Alzheimer's Disease**

Do not add drop shadows

**Advancing Solutions for
Alzheimer's Disease**

Do not use Black in place of Dark Blue in text

**Advancing Solutions for
Alzheimer's Disease**

Do not outline typography

Advancing Solutions for
Alzheimer's Disease

PHOTOGRAPHY

The three approved AD-RIDDLE photography groups consists of Doctors, Doctors and Individuals, and Individuals. These photographs are approved for use across all communications online and in print. AD-RIDDLE photography should always feel warm, human, positive, and be well-lit.

When choosing new photography, build off the categories shown here and always ensure to select options that feel inclusive and reflect a mix of race, gender, and age.

1. Doctors

Options 1a-1c

Options 1d-1f

2. Doctors and Individuals

Options 2a-2c

Options 2d-2f

PHOTOGRAPHY

The three approved AD-RIDDLE photography groups consists of Doctors, Doctors and Individuals, and Individuals. These photographs are approved for use across all communications online and in print. AD-RIDDLE photography should always feel warm, human, positive, and be well-lit.

When choosing new photography, build off the categories shown here and always ensure to select options that feel inclusive and reflect a mix of race, gender, and age.

3. Individuals

Options 3a-3c

Options 3d-3f

Options 3g-3i

Options 3j-3l

PHOTOGRAPHY DO NOT'S

Avoid the following when creating AD-RIDDLE communications online and in print.

Do not use photography that is too dark

Do not use staged or cliché photography

Do not use photography with a negative tone

Do not use washed out photography

Do not use black and white photography

Do not use illustration in place of photography

PATHWAY GRAPHIC

The Pathway Graphic is a modular Light Red line derived from the AD-RIDDLE logotype. It is approved for use across all communications online and in print. The Pathway Graphic represents the journey towards better detection, diagnosis, and treatment of Alzheimer's disease.

The Pathway Graphic can be a hero element on document covers, websites, and social graphics, or used in smaller amounts as a detail element in smaller communications.

The Pathway Graphic can be expressed in many ways that vary in complexity, from a single line, to overlapping lines. It should always have right angles and enter and exit along two margins in a communication.

The Pathway Graphic should always be Light Red. Shown here are the approved background colors which include Dark Blue, Light Blue, and White.

The Pathway Graphic should always have a substantial line thickness scaled according to the communication that is being created. Do not create Pathway Graphics that are too thick or too thin. In smaller communications, such as online banners, always use a simpler composition.

The Pathway Graphic can be combined with photography for more dynamic communications. See page 14 for usage examples.

When creating Pathway Graphics, always keep the following rules in mind:

- Ensure it has an enter and exit point along two margins
- Use only Light Red for color
- Use a substantial line thickness scaled according to the communication
- Use simpler compositions in smaller communications

Shown here are approved examples of how the Pathway Graphic can be used across applications varying in size and format.

16:9 ratio PowerPoint, video

8.5 x 11" / A4 document

33 x 81" / 80 x 200 cm standing banner

120 x 600 px banner

300 x 250 px banner

1080 x 1080 social graphic

728 x 90 px banner

PATHWAY GRAPHIC DO NOT'S

Avoid the following when creating AD-RIDDLE communications online and in print.

Do not make line thickness too thick or thin

Do not create compositions that are too complex

Do not use angles or rounded corners

Do not add drop shadow

Do not use non-approved colors

Do not place over complex photography

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Annex 2 – ARTICLE 17: COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, OPEN SCIENCE AND VISIBILITY

Dissemination

Dissemination of results

The beneficiaries must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests.

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

Additional dissemination obligations

Where the call conditions impose additional dissemination obligations, the beneficiaries must also comply with those.

Open Science

Open science: open access to scientific publications

The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. In particular, they must ensure that:

- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) and
- information is given via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

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	Author(s): Angela Bradshaw and Cindy Birck (11-Alzheimer Europe)	Security: PU	30/34

Metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machineactionable) and provide information at least about the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

Only publication fees in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement.

Open science: research data management

The beneficiaries must manage the digital research data generated in the action ('data') responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles and by taking all of the following actions:

- establish a data management plan ('DMP') (and regularly update it)
- as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, deposit the data in a trusted repository; if required in the call conditions, this repository must be federated in the EOSC in compliance with EOSC requirements
- as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, ensure open access — via the repository — to the deposited data, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a licence with equivalent rights, following the principle 'as open as possible as closed as necessary', unless providing open access would in particular:
 - be against the beneficiary's legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation, or
 - be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests or the beneficiary's obligations under this Agreement; if open access is not provided (to some or all data), this must be justified in the DMP
- provide information via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to re-use or validate the data.

Metadata of deposited data must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.

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Open science: additional practices

Where the call conditions impose additional obligations regarding open science practices, the beneficiaries must also comply with those.

Where the call conditions impose additional obligations regarding the validation of scientific publications, the beneficiaries must provide (digital or physical) access to data or other results needed for validation of the conclusions of scientific publications, to the extent that their legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded (and unless they already provided the (open) access at publication).

Where the call conditions impose additional open science obligations in case of a public emergency, the beneficiaries must (if requested by the granting authority) immediately deposit any research output in a repository and provide open access to it under a CC BY licence, a Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent. As an exception, if the access would be against the beneficiaries' legitimate interests, the beneficiaries must grant nonexclusive licenses — under fair and reasonable conditions — to legal entities that need the research output to address the public emergency and commit to rapidly and broadly exploit the resulting products and services at fair and reasonable conditions. This provision applies up to four years after the end of the action (see Data Sheet, Point 1).

Plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results including communication activities

Unless excluded by the call conditions, the beneficiaries must provide and regularly update a plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results including communication activities.

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Annex 3 – Example of an AD-RIDDLE Communications Toolkit

AD-RIDDLE LAUNCH TOOLKIT

Thank you for your partnership as we prepare to launch AD-RIDDLE! We would appreciate your help in spreading the word about the project on launch day, scheduled for Thursday 25 January at 12pm CET (6am ET).

Below, you'll find guidance for posting about or engaging with AD-RIDDLE on our social media channels ([Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#)), as well as some sample social media posts, images of the catalogue, and other resources that may be of use.

General guidance:

- Please consider resharing or engaging with posts from the AD-RIDDLE channels; content will be published **on JANUARY 25 at 12PM CET/6AM ET**.
- Please follow our channels and tag AD-RIDDLE when posting about us ([@AD_RIDDLE](#) on Twitter/X, and [AD-RIDDLE](#) on LinkedIn).
- Feel free to tag leaders/researchers on your team or other partners you're working with as relevant!
- If you wish to include an image or graphic, feel free to adapt the quote card template with a short partner quote about AD-RIDDLE - or use the partner logo image below.

Important links:

- AD-RIDDLE website: www.ad-riddle.org
- AD-RIDDLE LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/ad-riddle>
- AD-RIDDLE X (Twitter): [@AD_RIDDLE](#)
- AD-RIDDLE contact: info@ad-riddle.org

Key messages: Below are some key messages about AD-RIDDLE that may help you shape your own social media posts about the project.

- AD-RIDDLE is a new IHI-funded initiative aiming to revolutionise the way Alzheimer's disease is detected, diagnosed, prevented and treated.
- AD-RIDDLE aims to unlock efficiencies for AD diagnosis and treatment, removing barriers to entry that traditionally slow down patient access to healthcare providers and precision medicine.
- AD-RIDDLE will offer healthcare providers a modular toolbox platform of validated resources and personalised interventions to help prevent and treat Alzheimer's disease.
- The AD-RIDDLE platform will allow for flexible adaptation and application in diverse settings, from memory clinics to primary care and the broader population outside of healthcare systems.
- The AD-RIDDLE consortium unites academic and industry partners, healthcare providers, regulatory bodies, and patient organisations, bringing together a mix of world-class research, clinical practice, diagnostics, advanced analytics and data platform capabilities.

Example social posts:

These posts are meant to be inspiration for your own social posts. Feel free to use them as a starting place, but we recommend avoiding copy-pasting them - we don't want everyone to share the same thing!

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LinkedIn:

@AD-RIDDLE is a groundbreaking collaboration between 24 partners to bridge the gap between Alzheimer’s research, implementation science, and precision medicine. Now more than ever, patients need to be matched with the right interventions at the right time—our work aims to make that possible.

You can follow our journey at www.ad-riddle.org. Congratulations to everyone involved - I’m looking forward to our next 5 years of collaboration!

X (Twitter):

Now more than ever, #Alzheimers patients need to be matched with the right interventions at the right time. @AD_RIDDLE aims to make that possible. Follow along at <http://www.ad-riddle.org/>!

Graphics:

Feel free to use one of the images below in your communications, or create your own quote card using the provided template!

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AD-RIDDLE will rapidly advance the “last mile” of innovation in Alzheimer’s care pathways, building on high-quality data and bridging research to the real-world setting. AD-RIDDLE will generate evidence for clinical implementation of precision diagnostics, interventions and therapies, and drive new research on Alzheimer’s disease by making datasets available through EPND.”

—Niranjan Bose
Project Co-Lead, Gates Ventures

With new research on efficacy of lifestyle interventions and the promise of disease-modifying therapeutics, there is renewed hope for patients, caregivers, and medical providers, and a window of opportunity for substantial progress. AD-RIDDLE represents the greatest opportunity yet for cross-sector progress in Alzheimer’s research and care.”

—Miia Kivipelto
Project Co-Lead, Karolinska Institutet